

Kinetics and mechanism of electron transfer reactions : Ruthenium(III) catalyzed oxidation of butanone by peroxomonosulphate in acid aqueous medium – Discrimination between keto-enol tautomerism

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Abstract : Kinetics of oxidation of cyclohexanone by peroxomonosulphate has been studied in acid perchlorate medium. The kinetic rate laws based on the proposed mechanisms are similar. This reaction is second order in nature. A plausible reaction mechanism has been suggested. The preferred mode of electron transfer is via keto and not by enol form of the ketones and thus keto-enol tautomerism does not play any role.

Activation parameters such as energy and entropy of activation have been calculated.

Keywords : Kinetics, mechanism, ketones, peroxomonosulphate, keto-enol tautomerism.

Introduction

Recently Jaky and co-workers¹ have questioned the oxidation mechanism of ketones by permanganate and other oxidants in acid medium²⁻⁶. It is still an open question whether nucleophilic addition or substitution on α -carbon atom is associated with oxidation in carbonyl reactions. In acidic medium enolization of ketone is generally considered to be the rate controlling step in certain reactions⁷⁻¹⁴ whereas proposals based on radical mechanism¹⁵⁻¹⁸ have also been made. Also, enolization and formation of radicals are assumed to be the rate determining steps in alkaline media.

Peroxoacids are compounds of considerable potential. Peroxomonosulphate is considered to be a substituted H_2O_2 with the replacement of one of its hydrogens by $-SO_3$ group. The acid is dibasic and its two ionizable protons resemble to that of H_2SO_4 and H_2O_2 respectively.

Peroxides act as oxygen donors to organic substrates, in bleaching and in decontamination, weakness of $-O-O-$ bond in peroxoacids is mainly responsible for its reactions. H_2O_2 which is the parent analog of this important class of per acids¹⁹⁻²¹ is a strong oxidizing agent in either acid or alkaline solutions, latter reactions are relatively faster. However, the chemistry of peroxomonosulphuric acid is less understood than that of peroxodisulphate.

In view of these observations we undertook the kinetics study of oxidation of certain ketones by peroxomonosulphate in acidic medium from the view-point of logical mechanistic proposals.

Experimental

Peroxomonosulphate under the trade name 'OXONE' (Aldrich) is a triple salt of the composition of $2KHSO_5$, $KHSO_4$, K_2SO_4 . The purity of the sample was tested both iodometrically and cerimetrically to 96%. Since earlier attempts²² failed to get a pure salt, no further attempts were, therefore, made. H_2O_2 is considered to be the hydrolytic product of PMS. However, H_2O_2 was tested negative eliminating the chances of hydrolysis of PMS under the experimental conditions of the title reaction. The hydrolysis has also earlier been ruled out²³ in case of PMS stability in moderate acidic solutions.

Also, the solution did not indicate any decomposition even on standing for *ca.* 24 h under ambient conditions. Nevertheless, a fresh solution of PMS was always employed in kinetic study.

All other reagents employed in this study were either of AnalaR or guaranteed reagent grade and were used as supplied. Doubly distilled water was employed throughout the study; the second distillation was from alkaline permanganate water in an all glass still.

Reactions were carried out in glass stoppered Erlenmeyer flasks thermostated in a water-bath at ± 0.1 °C unless stated otherwise. The reactions were initiated by temperature pre-equilibrated solution of PMS.

An aliquot (5 or 10 cm³) of the reaction mixture was withdrawn at different time intervals and then added in to KI solution (~10%) followed by addition of 1 cm³ of the mixed catalyst (Cu^{II} + Fe^{II}) solution. The liberated iodine was titrated against thiosulphate solution using starch as an indicator without any interference from other components of the reaction mixture. The iodine liberated by the mixed catalyst was accounted for in subsequent calculations. Initial rates were computed employing plane mirror method²⁴. Pseudo-first order and second order plots were made wherever reaction conditions permitted. The kinetics was studied for more than two half-lives of the reactions. The results in triplicate were reproducible to within $\pm 4\%$.

Stoichiometry :

The stoichiometry of the reaction was studied by identification of the oxidation products of the substrates under kinetics conditions. The oxidation products in case of butanone were qualitatively identified to be acetic acid as tested by IR spectral analysis.

Results

The concentration of peroxomonosulphate was varied in the range $(1.0-5.0) \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients at 35°C. Initial rates (k_i , mol dm⁻³ s⁻¹) were computed by plane mirror method and were found to be independent of the oxidant concentration conforming zero order dependence with respect to butanone. Thus the order with respect to PMS in butanone is zero.

The concentration of butanone was varied in the range $(2.0-10.0) \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³ at fixed concentrations of other ingredients and $[Ru^{III}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm⁻³, at 35°C. A plot of initial rate (k_i) against the concentration of the butanone yielded a straight line passing through the origin indicating first order dependence with respect to butanone.

The concentration of ruthenium(III) chloride (here to fore written as Ru^{III}) was varied from 1.0×10^{-5} to 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ in reaction of butanone. A plot of initial rate against the concentration of $[Ru^{III}]$ yielded a straight line passing through the origin indicating first order dependence with respect to the catalyst.

The concentration of hydrogen ion was varied by employing perchloric acid at $I = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³ (I is the ionic strength adjusted by lithium perchlorate) in case of butanone employing lithium perchlorate and also at 30, 35 and 40 °C respectively. The rate increases with increasing hydrogen ion concentration.

The concentration of lithium perchlorate was varied from 0.1 to 2.0 mol dm⁻³ in case of butanone at 35 °C. The rate increases with increasing concentration of lithium perchlorate.

The energy of activation was calculated to be (54 ± 3) kJ mol⁻¹ and the entropy of activation was also calculated to be (-67 ± 8) JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ in butanone in a conventional manner.

Discussion

The hydrolysis of peroxomonosulphate as represented²⁵ by eq. (1) is reported to take place even in neutral conditions in several days²⁶. This concludes that the hydrolysis of HSO₅⁻ to H₂O₂ under experimental conditions does not take place.

Peroxomonosulphate is a dibasic acid in which the central sulphur atom is surrounded tetrahedrally by a perhydroxyl group, a hydroxyl group and two oxo groups²⁷.

The proton in HSO₅⁻ moiety is more acidic than other proton in hydrogen peroxide ($pK_2 = 9.4 \pm 1$) at 25 °C.

Thus the species of peroxomonosulphate are HSO₅⁻ and SO₅²⁻ and the proton in HSO₅⁻ is tightly held²⁸ due to an internal hydrogen bonding.

So far the ketones are concerned; the acid catalyzed enolization is well established. Since enolization is not the rate determining step in ruthenium(III) catalyzed oxidation of butanone by PMS in acidic medium, both ketonic as well as its protonated forms in view of hydrogen ion dependence appear to be the reactive forms of the ketones.

Mechanism of Ru^{III} catalyzed oxidation of butanone :

The kinetic features of ruthenium(III) catalyzed oxidation of butanone by peroxomonosulphate is as follows :

(i) The reaction exhibits first order dependence with respect to substrate and catalyst respectively. However, order with respect to the oxidant is zero. This shows that whatever is the species of peroxomonosulphate that is not significant for overall kinetics of the reaction.

(ii) The reaction is catalyzed by hydrogen ion.

(iii) Since the products do not affect the rate of the reaction, this eliminates any fast equilibrium preceded by the rate controlling step. If these observations are taken into account, the following mechanism accounts for the reaction events satisfactorily.

Such a mechanism leads to the rate law (4) or (5)

$$-\frac{d[\text{PMS}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1'K_1' [\text{butanone}] [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] [\text{H}^+] + k_2'K_2' [\text{butanone}] [\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] [\text{H}^+]^2}{(K_1 + [\text{H}^+])} \quad (4)$$

where $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]$ and $[\text{butanone}]$ are the gross analytical concentrations of the catalyst and substrate respectively and k' is second order rate constant.

$$k = \frac{k_1'K_1'[\text{H}^+] + k_2'K_2'K[\text{H}^+]^2}{(K_1 + [\text{H}^+])} \quad (5)$$

Since the equilibrium constant K_1' and K_2' are significantly small and $K_1 \ll [\text{H}^+]$, the eq. (5) is further reduced to eq. (6).

$$k = k_1 + k_2K[\text{H}^+] \quad (6)$$

where k' is an observed second order rate constant (Table 1).

A plot of k' versus $[\text{H}^+]$ was made from eq. (6) that yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 1) from which k_1 was calculated to be (4.0 ± 0.2) , (5.6 ± 0.2) and $(9.0 \pm 0.3) \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 30, 35 and 40 °C respectively. k_2K calculated from the gradient of the line are (3.8 ± 0.2) , (5.4 ± 0.3) and $(7.2 \pm 0.4) \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 30, 35 and 40 °C respectively.

Table 1. Zero order (k_1) and second order (k) rate constants in reaction of butanone with peroxomonosulphate catalyzed by ruthenium(III) chloride

$10^3 [\text{PMS}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^2 [\text{Butanone}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^6 (k_1)$ ($\text{mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	K ($\text{dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
		$[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.05 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	
1.0	5.0	1.77	0.71
1.5	5.0	1.77	0.71
2.0	5.0	1.77	0.71
2.5	5.0	1.77	0.71
3.0	5.0	1.77	0.71
3.5	5.0	1.77	0.71
4.0	5.0	1.77	0.71
4.5	5.0	1.77	0.71
5.0	5.0	1.77	0.71
2.0	2.0	0.71	0.71
2.0	2.5	0.89	0.71
2.0	3.0	1.07	0.71
2.0	3.5	1.20	0.69
2.0	4.0	1.40	0.70
2.0	4.5	1.60	0.71
2.0	5.0	1.77	0.69
2.0	6.0	2.07	0.69
2.0	7.0	2.40	0.69
2.0	8.0	2.81	0.70
2.0	10.0	3.47	0.69
3.0	3.0	1.05	0.70
3.0	3.5	1.20	0.69
3.0	4.0	1.43	0.72
3.0	4.5	1.61	0.71
3.0	5.0	1.77	0.72
3.0	6.0	2.08	0.69
3.0	7.0	2.40	0.69
3.0	8.0	2.81	0.70
3.0	10.0	3.50	0.70
4.0	4.0	1.43	0.71
4.0	4.5	1.61	0.71
4.0	5.0	1.77	0.70
4.0	6.0	2.06	0.69
4.0	7.0	2.38	0.68
4.0	8.0	2.86	0.71
4.0	10.0	3.57	0.71

The ' k ' values were obtained by initial rates.

So far the mode of electron transfer is concerned the following Scheme 1 accounts for the transfer of electron from the substrate to the oxidant.

Scheme 1

The activated complex for hydride ion transfer can be envisaged as (II).

Fig. 1. Effect of hydrogen ion. [PMS = 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³; [butanone] = 5.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [Ru^{III}] = 5.0×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 5.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [I] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³; ○, 30°; △, 35°; □, 40 °C.

Since the O-atom loosens the C-H bond on the carbon atom, it may be possible that proton elimination may render electron transfer more probable than hydride ion abstraction in the rate controlling step.

In conclusion,

(i) Oxidation can not proceed via enolization since neither the kinetics nor the composition of intermediate supports such a mechanistic view.

(ii) Nucleophilic addition is supported by acid catalysis.

(iii) Decomposition of the intermediate is the rate controlling step.

(iv) The intermediate is formed on the carbonyl carbon atom and not at the α -carbon owing to electrophilic substitution.

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Hemkar *et al.* : Kinetics and mechanism of electron transfer reactions : Ruthenium(III) catalyzed *etc.*

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